

Summary of stable transformation of indica rice cv Chinsurah Boro II.

Experiment	Callus age (mo)/ callus line	Plates bombarded (no.)	<i>hph</i> -resistant callus lines	GUS+ callus lines (no.)	Embryogenic lines (no.)	Plants (no.)	GUS+ plant lines (no.)	Fertile plants (no.)	Selectable marker gene	Nonselectable gene
1	8.5/1	8	13	10	3	16	1 (1) ^a	0	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	p40CSD35S- <i>gus</i>
2	9/1	4	5	4	0	-	-	-	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	p40CSD35S- <i>gus</i>
3	7.5/2	3	3	1	2	8	0	7	p <i>Ubi1-hph</i>	p <i>Ubi1-gus</i>
4	8/2	12	5	2	1	2	0	1	p <i>Ubi1-hph</i>	p <i>Ubi1-gus</i>
5	7.5/2	7	7	-	3	23	-	22	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV <i>b</i>
6	8/2	7	5	-	1	4	-	4	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
7	8.3/2	8	1	-	1	1	-	1	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
8	8.3/2	9	2	-	1	2	-	1	pEmu- <i>hph</i>	RRSV
9	5.3/3	7	3	-	3	17	-	13	p <i>Ubi1-hph</i>	RRSV
10	5.3/3	7	6	-	1	6	-	6	p <i>Ubi1-hph</i>	RRSV
Total		72	50	17	16	79	1	55		

^a Number in parentheses shows transgenic plant line expressing GUS when about 5 cm tall, but not at 20 cm tall. ^b Coding region of rice ragged stunt virus segment 5 driven by various promoters.

and BEU expansion were observed when the *hph* gene was driven by the Ubi 1 promoter, followed by Emu and then CaMV35S. In all three cases, expanding BEUs formed nodular structures indicative of regeneration. The Ubi 1>Emu>CaMV35S ranking

follows the relative levels of GUS expression driven by these promoters in our transient and stable expression studies. From this we infer that stronger promoters enable the most effective selection. The data show that about 2,000-4,000 BEUs 1 d

after shooting are required to achieve each hygromycin-resistant callus line and that such BEUs regenerate into fertile transgenic rice plants with 1-8 copies of the transgene. ■

Transfer of cytoplasmic male sterility in indica rice through protoplast fusion

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Cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) is widely used in hybrid seed production and requires routine transfer of CMS to new genetic backgrounds. Transfer of CMS through conventional breeding requires five to six backcrossings, taking 2-3 yr. However, a one-step transfer of CMS through asymmetric protoplast fusion can be used to shorten this period (Kyoizuka et al 1989).

Plant regeneration, from protoplasts of CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines.

Embryogenic calli initiated from the scutella obtained from mature embryos of CMS line V20A were repeatedly subcultured to make them friable. Five hundred 1,000-mg calli were used to initiate cell suspension, which was established after 3-4 mo of regular subculturing at a 4-5 d

interval. Protoplasts, which were isolated, purified, and cultured as described by Bhattacharjee and Gupta (1995), underwent sustained division into microcolonies that became macroscopic after 30-40 d. Protocalli differentiation was obtained 20-30 d after transfer to regeneration medium. Plants were transferred to pots where they flowered and produced sterile pollen grains. Likewise, protocols for protoplasts to plant systems were developed for RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36.

Inactivation of donor and recipient protoplasts and asymmetric fusion.

Because protoplasts of all four lines were dividing on culture, we standardized the dose for their inactivation to undertake asymmetric fusion. Protoplasts of V20A were irradiated with 30 krad gamma ray (Fig. 1a); those of RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36 were inactivated with 10 mM iodoacetamide for 15 min at 20°C (Fig. 1b).

Fusion of gamma ray- and iodoacetamide-inactivated protoplasts of V20A with RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36 was attained with 25 V/1 KHz AC amplitude for 25 s, followed by 900 V DC pulse (2.52 KV/cm field strength) amplitude for 30 µs. Seven 10% fusions were obtained.

Culture of fusion products and plant regeneration, from putative cybrid calli.

Fused protoplasts of V20 A with RCPL1-2C, V20 B, and IR36, along with inactivated protoplasts of V20 A, V20 B, RCPL1-2C, and IR36, were cultured separately. The inactivated protoplasts served as the control. Only fused protoplasts underwent sustained division and formed microcolonies (Fig. 1c), which became macroscopic after 25-30 d of culture. Macrocolonies of putative cybrids between V20A and IR36 differentiated into plantlets when transferred to regeneration medium (Fig. 1d). The plantlets transferred to pots (Fig. 1e) grew to maturity and, as expected, were fertile. Putative cybrid calli between V20 A/RCPL1-2C and V20A/V20 B also differentiated and gave rise to plantlets, which were grown to maturity to check the expression of male sterility. Molecular analyses of mitochondrial DNA of both the sets and parents are in progress.

Cited reference

Bhattacharjee B, Gupta HS. 1995. Fertile plants regenerated from protoplasts of cold-tolerant rice line RCPL1-2C. *J. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 4:61-65. ■

Protoplast fusion between V20 A and IR36 and regeneration of putative cybrid. (a) gamma-irradiated protoplasts of V20 A; (b) iodoacetamide-treated protoplasts of IR36; (c) microcolonies resulting from sustained division of the fusion product; (d) plantlets regenerated from putative cybrid calli; and (e) putative cybrid plants.

Characters of plants regenerated from protoplasts of photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile rice

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Identifying photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) in rice (Shi 1981) makes it possible to produce hybrid rice seed through the two-line system. We studied the response of PGMS protoplast clones to photoperiod and temperature,

variation in ploidy, and agronomic traits. Promising PGMS line Zhenongdal 1s (X126-11) has already been developed through protoplast culture.

A cell suspension with small globular calli was established from the scutellum of mature embryos of PGMS cultivar N5047s. A high density ($1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ ml}^{-1}$) of protoplasts was obtained, and green regenerates (plantlets) were produced following Xue and Earle's (1995) method. To distinguish autotetraploids from diploids, the DNA content of regenerates was measured using flow cytometry according to the procedure of Arumugamuthan and Earle (1991). Sowing at different times under natural conditions at Hangzhou ($30^\circ 15' \text{ N}$) promoted changes in fertility and agronomic traits of the four diploid PGMS protoplast clones and their control cultivar N5047s.

Variation in ploidy. Flow cytometric analysis indicated that nuclear DNA content in protoplasts of diploid plants ranged between 0.715 and 0.873 $\text{pg } 2c^{-1}$, and that from autotetraploids ranged between 1.537 and 1.786 $\text{pg } 2c^{-1}$. This accounted for 60% diploid plants and 40% autotetraploid plants. Diploid regenerates were taller (78.0 cm) compared with the autotetra-

ploids (44.5 cm). The diploid plants had 96.5 spikelets per panicle whereas autotetraploids had few spikelets (19.3).

Change in fertility. Typical sterile pollen was >85% at the sterile stage and ranged from 10 to 30% at the fertile stage. However, the spherical sterile pollen ranged from 5 to 20% at the two stages. Percentage of staining pollen exhibited one or three peaks at the fertile stage. Four PGMS protoplast clones had obvious differences both in duration of sterility and in stability before mid-August. The change from sterility to fertility was clear. Seed set was more than 30% under shorter daylength in September.

Agronomic traits. Agronomic characters significantly differed among the four diploid protoplast clones and control cultivar N5047s. Spikelets panicle^{-1} , panicle number plant^{-1} , spikelet density, and 100-grain weight of X126-11 were significantly higher than those of other protoplast clone and NS047s.

Photoperiod and temperature responses. We used computer simulation analysis of PGMS protoplast clones to measure photoperiod-sensitive and temperature-sensitive coefficients for defining their model of seed set rate. The

Comparison of the anatomical structure of anther connective tissue and thrum at the fertile and sterile stages X126-11. (a) Fertile anther connective tissue, (b) sterile anther connective tissue, (c) fertile thrum, and (d) sterile thrum. NVB = normal vascular bundle. AVB = abnormal vascular bundle. V = vascular bundle. S = sieve tubes.